

LANGUAGE ACTIVITIES IN HOME READING ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract: This article focuses on the effective ways of Home reading lessons. By investigating the role of activities in Home reading lessons. Such activities help teachers to create English atmosphere in the class. Home reading lessons develop critical thinking, reading skills and raise awareness of good behavior Language activities are important to teach Home reading lessons for Teens 7. By reading stories any learner knows about classic and contemporary literature.

Key words: Home reading, twin's method, matching activity, reading skill, shapes, answer question, good behavior, story, character, literature, teens, motivate.

Introduction. As you know EFL teachers come across several questions about teaching English for young learners, teens and students. How do they teach English to improve during lessons and sessions? You know that today we have Home reading lessons for teens 7. Language activities in English lessons are efficient motivators of increasing learners' interest to reading Home reading stories... Language activities with effective methods are the daily part of teaching English. EFL teacher should not forget that all of them depend on the interests, feelings and actions of learners. To my mind Home reading lessons are new so teens have obstacles reading stories well. Home reading lessons develop critical thinking, raise awareness good behavior and develop reading skills. Moreover, by learning stories teens learn classic and contemporary literature. When you have Home reading tasks matching activities with shapes help to consolidate their knowledge about reading stories. They also make Home reading lessons interesting and fun. Usually EFL teachers are always ready to improve English with different ways to create English atmosphere and motivating Home reading lessons. Language activities play important role in English lessons. These activities never make teens get bored. Giving learners interesting tasks such as matching activity, you can motivate them to read Home reading stories. Teens are keen on working shapes, stickers, cards, making creative work, matching and describe characters. Working with learners interesting tasks during classes can bring to overcome challenges and make better results to encourage pupils. One of the new things introduced in Teens English 7 is Home Reading given after each unit. Today learners enjoy reading the texts to represent a real mix classical and contemporary literature. Home reading stories are interesting with several events or accidents. If

learners gain literature books they can share their ideas logically with anyone. Matching activities are much more fun than the traditional method to develop reading skills introduced story

David Copperfield. David Copperfield was born in a village in England. His father died before he was born. He went best school in the village. When David was six years old his mother was married a man by the name Mudstone. Mudstone did not like him and he did not like him. Mudstone decided to send him to a boarding school. Next day he sent him there. He was in boarding school for two years. Then he heard about his mother's death. Mudstone sitting on a chair said that his mother died. When he came Mudstone, he said that he must start working. Because he had no money for education. David Copperfield was in London streets without money, food or home. His mother told him that his aunt lived in Dover. She was his father's sister. David went to his aunt's house. It was morning when David came to his aunts. She was in the garden, when she saw a poor boy looking at her. She asked: What is it boy? What do you want? David said: I`m David Copperfield, your nephew. He told her everything. He gave him hot water in the bath and some food.

As days went by Miss Trotwood put David in a good school and looked after him well. Her friend Wicker den and his daughter Agnes helped him. David and Agnes became great friends. Wicker den was a rich man. Wicker den was happy that David saved his money and house. A few years later David and Agnes, who were in love with each other for along.

As you see, during each lesson or class teachers should spend exact time for developing learners reading skills. What kind activity can teacher do?

Memory words. One example of such an activity is,, Write and Rub “.According to this word game teacher should write words belong to the story which teens learnt at home. You write on the blackboard. Teacher asks and rubs out one word by one. Pupils find written words. Asking time words teacher can guess Who has worked on vocabulary? By this activity you can define and teach all the words in every field of our life.

Words:

1. to die 4. food 7.poor
2. to be married 5. Home 8. nephew
3. left 6. Rich 9. money

Answer the questions

We can assess learners the activity answer the questions.

1. Who was David Copperfield?
2. How old was David when his father died?
3. How old was he when he was left in London streets?
4. Who was Mudstone?

5. What kind of a father was he?

6. How did David find out where Miss Trotwood live?

“Twins question”

According to this method there are two mixed questions. Teacher divides two groups. Two pupils come and choose questions and make up parts of questions.

Student A

When his father died?

What was David’s relationship with Miss Trot Wood and

Student B

How did he come to live with her?

How old was David?

Students match parts of questions and they join colored shapes.

Student A

What was David’s relationship with Miss Trotwood and how did he come to live with her?

Student B

How old was David when his father died?

Like “Twins questions” teacher gives colored shape parts of questions learners from group, they join and answer questions. So, teens guess the main idea of the story and make up parts of questions. Questions always are keys of solving problems teaching English. From teaching observations EFL teachers know that learners usually do these kinds of activities with great interest.

“Matching sentences”

By, “Matching sentences” activity learners can assess clause sentences in grammar through in the story. Following activity matching sentence is the secret of this task.

Teens match and join sentences and looked after him well As days went by, Miss Trotwood put David in a good school

Answer: As days went by, Miss Trotwood put David in a good school and looked after him well.

Matching sentences are good way to improve gaining clause sentences.

Examples :1. His father died before he was born. 2. When David was six years old, his mother married a man by the name Mudstone.

“Describe characters”

Language activity helps to be in good behavior and encourage them to be hero today. Write five sentences about story characters.

The character is a good boy. He is hard working. He found his aunt where she lived in Dover. He studied in difficult situation. He saved house and money of Mr. Wicker den. (David)

Conclusion. To sum up language activities are important in teaching practice.

Reading is the best way in lessons. New effective methods are taught in order to motivate learners Home reading stories to be initiative and feel happy themselves during English lessons.

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